

GUIDED checklist

Manuscript: Developing a Place-Based Audio Guide to Support Nature Engagement: Intervention Content and Programme Theory

Scope note: This checklist is completed for the intervention development study reported in the manuscript. It documents the development context, evidence and theory inputs, stakeholder involvement, refinement process, and remaining uncertainties.

Guideline source: Duncan, E., O'Cathain, A., Rousseau, N., Croot, L., Sworn, K., Turner, K. M., Yardley, L., & Hoddinott, P. (2020). Guidance for reporting intervention development studies in health research (GUIDED): an evidence-based consensus study. *BMJ open*, 10(4), e033516. <https://doi.org/10.1136/bmjopen-2019-033516>

Item	GUIDED item description	Explanation	Where addressed in manuscript	Other / supplementary material
1	Report the context for which the intervention was developed.	Understanding the context in which an intervention was developed informs readers about the suitability and transferability of the intervention to the context in which they are considering evaluating, adapting or using the intervention. Context here can include place, organizational and wider socio-political factors that may influence the development and/or delivery of the intervention.	Abstract; Introduction; Methods: Intervention site; Stakeholder involvement and roles	
2	Report the purpose of the intervention development process.	Clearly describing the purpose of the intervention specifies what it sets out to achieve. The purpose may be informed by research priorities, evidence gaps, practice guidance or prioritisation exercises.	Abstract; Aim; Introduction	

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3	Report the target population for the intervention development process.	The target population is the population that will potentially benefit from the intervention. If clearly described, readers can understand the relevance of the intervention to their own research or practice. Health inequalities, gender and ethnicity may be relevant features.	Abstract; Introduction; Pilot study; Intervention site	
4	Report how any published intervention development approach contributed to the development process.	Many formal intervention development approaches exist and are used to guide intervention development. Where a formal approach is used, describe the process followed, including deviations. It is helpful to give a rich description of how any published approach was operationalised.	Methods: Reporting and methodological standards; Evidence inputs; Programme theory; Discussion	
5	Report how evidence from different sources informed the intervention development process.	Intervention development is often based on published evidence and/or primary data. Describe and reference all forms of evidence and data that informed development and explain how they were used.	Methods: Evidence inputs; Theories and empirical findings; Pilot study; Refinement of the guide and route design	Interview guide can be found in the supplementary material.

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6	Report how/if published theory informed the intervention development process.	Reporting whether and how theory informed the development process aids understanding of the theoretical rationale underpinning the intervention. Theory may include existing published theory or programme theory.	Methods: Theories and empirical findings; Core components; Programme theory; Discussion	
7	Report any use of components from an existing intervention in the current intervention development process.	Some interventions are developed with components adopted from existing interventions. Identify adopted/adapted components and original source to distinguish novel from existing components.	Introduction; Script development; Audio production workflow; References	
8	Report any guiding principles, people or factors that were prioritised when making decisions during the intervention development process.	Reporting guiding principles helps readers understand the reasoning behind decisions. These may include population views, modality, design features, scalability or delivery constraints.	Methods: Evidence inputs; Core components; Script development; Audio production workflow; Intervention site; Refinement of the guide and route design	
9	Report how stakeholders contributed to the intervention development process.	Potential stakeholders include patient/community representatives, policy makers, health care providers, commissioners and others. Specify how groups contributed and their degree of influence.	Methods: Stakeholder involvement and roles; Pilot study; Acknowledgements; Refinement of the guide and route design	

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10	Report how the intervention changed in content and format from the start of the intervention development process.	Intervention development is often iterative. Describe how content and format changed from the beginning to the end of development.	Pilot study; Refinement of the guide and route design; Script development; Audio production workflow	
11	Report any changes to interventions required or likely to be required for subgroups.	Specify changes perceived as required for delivery or tailoring to specific subgroups, including personnel, content, mode of delivery or format.	Intervention site; Audio production workflow; Pilot study; Refinement of the guide and route design; Discussion	
12	Report important uncertainties at the end of the intervention development process.	List remaining uncertainties such as intensity, mode of delivery, materials, procedures or suitable location. This can guide future research and practice.	Programme theory; Discussion; Conclusion	
13	Follow TIDieR guidance when describing the developed intervention.	Interventions have often been poorly reported. TIDieR guidance should therefore be followed when describing a developed intervention.	Methods: Reporting and methodological standards; Supplementary material: TIDieR checklist	TIDieR checklist for the audio-based engagement guide component can be found in the supplementary material.
14	Report the intervention development process in an open access format.	Open-access reporting increases accessibility, visibility and cumulative learning about intervention development methodology.	The manuscript is submitted to an open-access publishing platform.	